
Influence Of Gender And Educational Qualification On Teacher's Self-Efficacy In Tertiary Level Colleges

Mrs. Niharika Garg*

Dr. Shashi Malik**

Abstract

The study investigated the Influence of Gender and Educational Qualification on teacher's self-efficacy in tertiary level colleges. The degree colleges are affiliated to C.C.S. University Meerut, which are selected by randomization. Total 8 colleges were selected. The target population was represented government/aided teachers included male and female both. The sample included 31 male and 44 female teachers who were randomly selected from both traditional and professional courses. To measure the impact on teachers' self-efficacy, we used Teachers' sense of self-efficacy scale (TSES) developed by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001). This instrument was adapted in Indian conditions. The reliability of adapted tool was .894, which indicates the good internal consistency of tool. Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs analysis in Instructional strategies, Classroom management and Student engagement. As previous studies find the relationship or impact of various variables as gender, teaching experiences etc. at secondary level of education on teachers' self-efficacy. The objective of current study is to find out the impact of gender and educational qualification on teachers' sense of self-efficacy at tertiary level colleges and also analysis the sense of self-efficacy at this level of education. The finding of the study shows that the t-value of male and female teachers' self-efficacy has no difference, also Ph.D and non Ph.D teachers are equal on their level of self efficacy beliefs.

Keywords: Teacher's sense of self-efficacy, Gender, Educational Qualification, Tertiary level of education.

Introduction

'I can do this...' this statement shows the self-efficacy of a person. When we think about our potential, our perception, we just want to do things easily; this concept shows the concept of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is the personal belief of possessing the ability to perform professional tasks with effectiveness and skillfully. Bandura (1977) noted that self-efficacy beliefs have a great impact on people's cognitive, motivation, affective and selection processes. Since its introduction, the construct of self-efficacy has been conceptualized as a significant variable for predicting an individual's behavior (Bandura, 1977). Self-efficacy plays a major role in teaching and learning process that continues to intrigue researchers and practitioners. Previous researches have provided much evidence in supporting the effectiveness of teacher self-efficacy, or the extent to which a teacher believes that he or she can influence the students' outcome, in educational contexts (Podell & Soodak, 1993; Muijs & Reynolds, 2001; Tschannen-Moran & Hoy 2001). Studies have indicated that teacher self-efficacy has been associated with teacher effort and persistence in encountering difficulties (Gibson & Dembo, 1984; Podell & Soodak, 1993), self-efficacy beliefs and academic

* Research Scholar, Dept. of Education, V.M.L.G.College, Ghaziabad

** Associate Professor, Dept. of Education, V.M.L.G.College, Ghaziabad

performance and persistence (Martin & Marsh, 2006; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2004), professional commitment (Evans & Tribble, 1986), openness to new methods in teaching and positive teacher behavior (Guskey, 1988) and using more humanistic, positive, or teacher-based strategies to deal with student problems (Woolfolk, Rosoff, & Hoy, 1990).

In educational perspectives, teacher self-efficacy can be conceptualized as an individual teacher's beliefs in his or her ability to think, to plan, to organize, and to carry out activities that are required to attain the educational goals (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010). On their part, Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001) observed that teacher self-efficacy is a teacher's judgment of his or her capability to bring about desired outcome of student engagement and learning. Bandura (1995) explained that teachers' beliefs about their efficacy can be developed from four main sources of influence. These sources are: (1) mastery experiences with which individuals can gauge their capabilities; (2) vicarious experiences that give individuals comparison information to use in judging their competence; (3) social persuasions that others might use to help convince an individual that he/she possesses the ability to perform a certain task; and (4) physiological and emotional states that serve as another indicator of capability. These four informative principal sources provide a framework for theoretical and empirical studies on teachers' self-efficacy beliefs. Bandura's concept of self-efficacy defines a belief or behavior that executes the required outcomes. When we talk about teacher self-efficacy or teacher's belief about their abilities to produce expected students' outcomes, there are many factors that influence the belief or the sense of self-efficacy of teachers. Teachers' sense of self-efficacy or their judgments about their abilities to promote students' learning was identified over two decades ago as one of the few teacher characteristics associated with student achievement (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2007). Teacher's sense of efficacy is a powerful belief that affects teaching and learning environment, teacher educators, administrators, students' outcomes and policy makers.

Review of related Literature

There are many studies related to Teachers' sense of self-efficacy. Bandura's (1989) social cognitive theory defined the concept of self-efficacy. Teacher self-efficacy has been defined as the extent to which a teacher is confident enough to his or her ability to promote students' learning (Bandura, 1994). According to Bandura, human behavior is motivated by the interaction of two kinds of expectations: Self efficacy and outcome expectancy; the former referring to peoples' judgments of their capability to undertake and execute successfully a specific task in a specific context, and the latter including judgments about the likely consequences that this performance would bring about (Bandura, 1993).

Many Researches have been conducted as teachers with high level of self-efficacy are more likely to divide the class into small groups rather than teaching the class as a whole, thereby allowing the opportunity for more individualized instruction (Tschannen-Moran, 2001).

Nejati, Hassani and Sahrapour (2014) conducted a study which examined the relationship between gender and subscales of teachers' self-efficacy. The sample represented the Iranian English as foreign language(EFL)teachers from private English language Institutes in karaj. There were 34 EFL teachers(male and female both). Researchers used Teachers' sense of self-efficacy tool to analysis the sense of self-efficacy of teachers. They found in their study that there is no difference in male and female at classroom management but there was difference at Student engagement and Instructional strategies. Moreover they also interpreted, male teachers were better at student engagement and female teachers at

Instructional strategies. Wolf, Foster and Birkenholz (2010) conducted a study to define the relationship between self-efficacy of agricultural education teachers in Ohio State University, USA. The sample of the study was 24 teachers during the 2007 fall quarter. Researcher used Teachers' sense of self-efficacy developed by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001). After analysis the result researcher interpret it as teachers has high level of self-efficacy at the point of experience. And they also found that teachers are more efficient at classroom management rather than efficient at student engagement and instructional strategies. Gurbuzturk and Sad (2009) also found in their study that there was significant difference in male and female at the level of self-efficacy. They also found that female teachers have higher efficacy than male teachers.

Chacon (2005) observed no relationship between self-efficacy and gender as they examined English Foreign Language teachers' responses in middle school of Venezuela. Karimvand (2011) also analyzed the result of his study, which was conducted on Iranian EFL teachers. He investigated the effects of gender and teachers' interaction effects on self-efficacy. It was found that teachers' gender had no significant interaction effect on the teachers' self-efficacy. He used regression analysis in his study. Similarly, Cubukcu (2008) was found in his study that there is no significant difference in term of gender and self-efficacy belief of foreign language teachers. On the other hand many researchers indicate different result. Tabak et al. (2003) found in their investigation female teachers have higher level of self-efficacy beliefs as compare to their male colleagues. Similarly Klassen and Chiu (2010) investigating the effects of self efficacy and job satisfaction in term of gender in their study. They found that female teachers have lower level of self-efficacy in classroom management but not in student engagement and instructional strategies.

Hamurcu (2006) also found a significant difference between male and female teachers of science teaching. Female teachers have higher self-efficacy rather than male teachers. Sarfo et al. (2015) found the relationship between gender and instructional strategies, classroom management and student engagement. They interpreted the result of their study as female teachers have high instructional strategies efficacy than student engagement and classroom management efficacy.

Objectives

1. To find out the impact of gender on teachers' sense of self-efficacy.
2. To find out the impact of educational qualification on teachers' sense of self- efficacy.
3. To know the sense of self efficacy in Tertiary level teachers.

Hypotheses

In the light of the objectives started earlier, the following hypotheses will be verified:

1. There are no gender differences in self-efficacy of teachers teaching at tertiary level of education.
2. There is no significant difference in tertiary education teachers' sense of self-efficacy with reference to educational qualification.

Methodology

The present study explores the influence of certain factors as gender and educational qualification on teachers' sense of self-efficacy in tertiary level colleges. The researcher adopted ex-post facto research method for the purpose because of the self-reporting nature of what already exist as self-efficacy in the tertiary education teachers.

The target population for the present study comprised all the tertiary level colleges' teachers working under Government/Aided colleges affiliated to CCS University, Meerut. First of

all, randomization was done to select the colleges from the list of tertiary level colleges of CCS University Meerut. Total 8 degree colleges were selected, and then total 75 teachers were taken in the sample through quota sampling considering view point of gender and educational qualification.

The tool used for collecting data from the teachers was adapted version of Teachers' Sense of Self-efficacy Scale that was originally developed by Megan Tschannen-Moran and Anita Woolfolk Hoy (2001). The tool was adapted in Indian conditions and final tool has 30 items which measured teachers' sense of efficacy in the areas of instructional strategies (10 items), classroom management (10 items) and students engagement (10 items) respectively. Teachers rated their responses on a 5-point Likert scale from 'Nothing' (1) to 'A great deal' (5).

This tool which was developed in the conditions of USA, hence its reliability and validity has to be re-established. A group of teachers (N=30) was selected for pilot study. The reliability of adapted tool was .894, which indicates the good internal consistency of tool.

The researcher explained the purpose of the study to teachers and they were assured that data collected from them will keep confidential and will be used only for research purpose. Then the researcher personally distributed the tool among the teachers in their respective colleges with good rapport. The responses collected from the teachers were scrutinized and analyzed statistically through MS excel. The researcher used both descriptive and inferential statistics for finding the answers of research questions. The descriptive statistics was used to obtain some summary information on respondents' gender and educational qualification whereas inferential statistics were used for testing for differences which was set at 0.05 significant levels. For verification of hypotheses, independent sample t-test was employed.

Results

The results are presented in Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4 under the headings of demographic characteristics of the teachers, teachers' self- efficacy dimension wise, gender differences in teachers' self-efficacy and educational qualification differences in teachers' self efficacy respectively.

Demographic Characteristics of Tertiary Level Teachers

The demographic characteristics of the respondents are shown as a table 1

Table: 1 Demographic Characteristics of Tertiary Level Teachers (N=75)

S.N.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Gender		
	Male	31	40.5
	Female	44	59.5
2.	Age(in years)		
	20-30	10	13.3
	30-40	24	32
	40-50	25	33.3
	50& above	16	21.3
3.	Education Qualification		
	Ph.D	48	64
	Non- Ph.D	27	36
4.	Teaching Experience		

	0-10	10	13.3
	10-20	19	25.3
	20-30	26	34.7
	30& above	20	26.6

From table 1, it shows that out of 75 respondents sample 31 (40.5%) are male and 44 (59.5%) are female. So it is clear that the majority of population sample is female teachers in degree colleges. Moreover, the age of respondents lies between 30-50 years, shows that the sample of this study is relatively young. When we talk about the educational qualifications of respondents it shows that there is the majority of higher education means Ph.D degree holders. Further teaching experience of teachers shows that degree college's teachers have good years of experience about 20 to 30 years. The implication of this sample shows clearly that teachers have long year working experiences and they have knowledge to describe their self-efficacy beliefs.

When we talk about teacher's self-efficacy beliefs, we just talk about not only their self motivation but also their management skills, their presence of mind, dealing with students, uses of techniques and strategies etc...In this study we measured teacher's self efficacy in three dimensions as: Instructional strategies, Classroom management and Student engagement (Tschannen-Moran &Woofolk Hoy's Teacher sense of self-efficacy scale). Table 2 shows that degree colleges teacher's mean scores with standard deviations of the three subscales.

Table 2: Self-Efficacy of Tertiary Level Teachers

	No. of respondents	Mean	SD
Teachers' Sense of Efficacy	75	199.3784	33.79742
Instructional Strategies	75	67.18919	13.08316
Classroom Management	75	66.48649	11.1604
Students Engagement	75	66.12162	13.09915

Here we can show the mean scores as gender and educational qualifications wise of degree colleges teachers as a graph:

Graph: 1

Findings on the Gender Difference in Tertiary level Teachers’ Self-efficacy

To determine the gender wise differences in teachers’ self-efficacy scores an independent sample t test was conducted. There are t test scores shown in table 3 as:

Table 3: Gender wise difference in teachers’ self-efficacy

Sub scale	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t	Significant at 0.05 level(two tailed)
Instructional Strategies	Male	31	64.56667	14.15842	73	0.153968	Not significant
	Female	44	69	12.14831			
Classroom Management	Male	31	63.43333	11.71996	73	0.051321	Not significant
	Female	44	68.56818	10.38648			
Student Engagement	Male	31	63.53333	13.79088	73	0.161943	Not significant
	Female	44	67.88636	12.45684			
TSES	Male	31	191.1667	34.09023	73	0.083373	Not significant
	Female	44	205.0227	32.80704			

This table 3 shows that t value is not significant. It means that there is a gender wise no significance difference in self-efficacy of the degree college’s teachers. We also conclude

that the mean score of female teachers($X=205.0227$) is higher than the male teachers of the degree colleges. Separately the table indicate that female teachers on average have a better instructional strategies efficacy ($X=69$; $SD=12.15$), classroom management ($X=68.56$; $SD=10.39$) and student engagement efficacies ($X=67.88$; $SD= 12.45$) than male teachers.

Finding on the Educational Qualification Difference in Tertiary Teachers' Self-efficacy

To determine the educational qualification wise differences in teachers' self-efficacy scores an independent sample t test was conducted. There are t test scores shown in table 4 as:

Table 4: Educational Qualification wise difference in teachers' self efficacy

Qualification	N	Mean	df	t value	Significant at 0.05 level(two tailed)
Ph.D	48	201.1224	73	0.097844	Not significant
Non-Ph.D	27	184.2963			

This table indicates that the t value at 0.05 level. It is concluded that qualification (Ph.D & Non Ph.D) wise no significance difference in the self-efficacy of the degree college's teachers. It is also indicates that the mean score of the Ph.D holders is higher than non Ph.D teachers.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to determine the impact of gender and educational qualification on tertiary level teachers' self efficacy. The study shows that there is no significance difference between male and female teachers' self efficacy. Further we analysis self efficacy beliefs scores of teaches as its three subscales, we find out that female teachers have better efficacies in Instructional strategies, Classroom management and students engagement. So we can say that male and female teachers did not differ as far as in term of self efficacy subscales. In overall teachers' self efficacy the result indicate that female teachers have relatively high mean score and it also indicate that they have adequate knowledge, effective skill of management and better teaching behavior. Further the result of study show that there is no significant difference between Ph.D and Non Ph.D of tertiary level teachers' self efficacy. The result revealed that Ph.D holders and non Ph.D holders teachers are equal on their level of self efficacy beliefs.

On the basis of this study it is recommended that at the higher level of education teachers should be efficient in Instructional strategies, Classroom management and Student engagement practices and should have high educational qualification and experiences.

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